

TECHNALOGY OF OBTAINING RED PIGMENT FROM MONASKUS AND PROSPECTS FOR DEVELOPMENT IN THE FOOD INDUSTRY

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Abstract: The fungus *Monascus purpureus* belongs to the phylum *Eucomycota*. These fungi are recognized for their fermented products and provide a variety of polyketide-type secondary metabolites. The yeast is used to prepare cholesterol-lowering statins in the commercial world. Statins, which are prescription drugs used to treat high cholesterol, have the same active ingredients as red yeast. During growth, *Monascus* spp break down the starch substrate into a range of metabolites, including secondary metabolites such as colours. *Monascus* pigment can be produced through solid state or submerged fermentation and then recovered, dried, and used. Thus, this chapter illustrates the entrepreneurship of *Monascus* pigment is characterized by the ability and willingness to start, organize, and run a *Monascus* pigment business, including all of its associated risks, in order profit.

Keywords: *Monascus* pigment, red yeast, solid state fermentation, submerged fermentation.

Introduction

Monascus purpureus is a fungus that belongs to the phylum *Eumycota* group or phylum, the *Ascomycotina* subphylum, the class *Ascomycetes*, the order *Eurotiales*, and the *Monascaceae* family. *Monascus pilosus*, *M. purpureus*, *M. ruber*, and *M. floricornis* are among the nine species of *Monascus*. *M. argentinensis*, *M. eremophilus*, *M. lunisporas*, *M. pallens*, and *M. sanguineus* are the three species listed, which has received critical appreciation on a global scale. These fungi are recognized for their fermented products and are a source of a variety of secondary metabolites of the polyketide type. The majority of higher fungi are heterokaryons, meaning they have genetically distinct nuclei that share the same mycelium. When the colonies of a fungus have genetically identical nuclei, the fungus is homokaryotic. Heterokaryosis has been demonstrated to produce filamentous fungus variety as well as metabolite instability or loss during fermentation operations.

M. purpureus belongs to the *Monascus* genus, which encompasses a group of fungus that are normally regarded asexual; yet, perfect forms (sexually reproducing forms) have been discovered. Similar to many fungi, *M. purpureus*' taxonomy is based mostly on visual qualities rather than biochemical and physiological properties or genetic makeup, which are commonly used to categorize bacteria. The yeast *Monascus purpureus* is utilized in the commercial manufacture of blood

cholesterol-lowering statins. Fungus is the most important because it is used in the creation of fermented foods in China in the form of red yeast rice. In healthy persons, red yeast is used to keep cholesterol levels in check. Red yeast contains the same active component as statins, which are prescription medications used to treat high cholesterol. As a result, red yeast comes with all of the toxicity, drug interactions, and warnings that come with this sort of treatment.

Monascus purpureus works by selectively inhibiting the enzyme that produces cholesterol. During the growth of *Monascus* spp, the starch substrate is degraded into a range of metabolites, including colours produced as secondary metabolites. The structure of pigments is influenced by the type of substrate used as well as a variety of other parameters such as pH, temperature, and moisture content during culture. This fungus is significant because it is used to make red yeast rice, which is a fermented dish popular in China. The structure of various *Monascus* pigments are given. Three strains of the fungus *Monascus purpureus* AKI, AKII, and 915 were chosen to produce angkak colours and lovastatin in potato dextrose agar (PDA) media. After that, the best fungal strain AKII has been used in three various rice media (Danuri, The *Monascus* pigment can be produced from naturally available substrates like rice, corn, whole sorghum grain (WSG), and dehulled sorghums (DSG). The grown fungi were used for the production of the *Monascus* pigment.

It was found by the studies conducted by Ignatius Srianta and the colleagues that *Monascus purpureus* grew well in rice grain compared to the other substrates (Srianta et al This chapter describes the many criteria and standards that must be met in order to commence a bio-business. It is currently a rapidly developing discipline that connects two huge domains: microbiology and business. It emphasizes how science, biology, and technology are all interconnected with business

Production of *Monascus* Pigment Raw Materials

The raw materials that are used for the growth of *Monascus* spp. are cheap and easily accessible. Raw materials have to be selected in such a way that they are cheap, so that funds can be saved. Compared to chemically synthesized compounds as raw materials, naturally available compounds could help with saving finance. *Monascus ruber* was tested for red pigment synthesis using a complex culture mix that included glucose or dextrose (10 g/L), corn steep liquor (5 or 10 g/L), and monosodium glutamate (0, 5.0, 7.6, 11.4, or 15.2 g/L). The extracellular red colour absorbance (20.7 U) and productivity (0.35 U/h) were best in a medium with 10 g/L sucrose, 5 g/L corn steep liquor, and 7.6 g/L monosodium glutamate. With analytical grade compounds, this medium also outperformed semi-synthetic media (12.4 U and 0.21 U/h). The cells grew in the same way in both mediums (6.5 g/L), showing that the more sophisticated culture media may produce more red pigments. Furthermore, when compared to the semi-synthetic medium, the complicated culture medium

accumulated fewer intracellular red pigments (9.1% and 30% respectively). Because of the cheap cost of the product and the lack of purification, the culture medium is almost certainly a considerable portion of the total cost in the synthesis of red pigment by *Monascus* sp. For example, raw fermentation medium from rice-based semisolid *Monascus* sp. cultures is employed directly as a red pigment. The purpose of this research is to create a complex culture medium for *Monascus ruber* that will allow it to manufacture red pigments, primarily using corn steep liquor, monosodium glutamate (to obtain water-soluble red pigments), and sucrose rather than glucose (to increase the production of certain red pigments and because sucrose is less expensive) (Hamano & Kilikian,).

Fermentation

Inoculating steamed rice grains spread on huge trays with a strain of *Monascus anka* and incubation for 20 days in an aerated and temperature-controlled environment is a traditional Chinese process. Moisture content, oxygen, and temperature are all important factors in these cultures carbon dioxide concentrations in the atmosphere, as well as the most significant aspect of cereal medium composition is parameters to regulate. The amount of moisture in the air is a critical factor. In plastic bags holding rice grains, red pigments were created. Pigmentation was only detected at a small scale. The initial moisture level was rather modest (26–32%). The water content of the substrates controlled initial pigmentation. It was observed that when the initial moisture level of the substrate increased, so did glucoamylase activity.

As a consequence of the large enzyme activity produced at high moisture content, glucose was promptly released in proportions that inhibited colouring. After that, the sugar was converted into ethanol (Dufossé et al.,). Due to the increased degree of starch hydrolysis, *Monascus* growth was greater on cooked autoclaved rice (4.4 OD/g) than on adequately sterilized rice (3.11 OD/g). High oxygen pressure (3.11 OD/g autoclaved rice) allowed for three times more growth than low oxygen pressure (1.14 OD/g autoclaved rice) in the experiment. Oxygen and carbon dioxide levels have a significant impact on pigment development and, to a lesser extent, growth on solid substrates such as rice. *Monascus* growth and pigment output are influenced by the initial pH of the substrate (Kaur et al.,).

Monascus cultivated on 50 g/L tapioca starch as a carbon source obtained a biomass dry weight of 8 g/L in a simple batch culture. When cell development slowed to 40 h, the red and yellow polyketide pigments were still generated, with OD units of 31 and 26.5, respectively. After 60 h of batch development, a 200 g/L starch medium was regularly supplied to a *Monascus* culture, and the biomass dry weight reached 16 g/L after 140 h. The concentration of red and yellow pigment was 70 and 60 OD units, respectively, at this moment. Mycelia were grown in a two-state (solid-liquid) batch bioreactor, with a solid state containing 400 g/L gelatinized starch

substrate and a liquid state containing all culture substrates except starch. The amylolytic enzymatic activity produced by the *Monascus* culture was used to degrade the starch block gently. The culture expanded at a reasonably consistent rate for the first 170 h, resulting in a cell concentration of 37.5 g/L and pigment concentrations of roughly 145 OD units for both red and yellow pigments.

Submerged Fermentation

Experiments were conducted to determine the best process parameters for producing colours from potato pomace and its sugar hydrolysate. After inoculating with 10 mL of spore suspension and incubating at 28 C, 200 rpm for seven days, the volume of media in the flask was 100 mL (Chen et al.). In 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks, submerged fermentation was conducted with 50 mL of raw rice straw part of the process fermentation medium. 2.5 g/L yeast extract, 2.5 g/L malt extract, 2.5 g/L peptone, 5 g/L K₂HPO₄, 0.1 g/L CaCl₂, 0.58 g/L MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.02 g/L FeSO₄·7H₂O, 0.02 g/L ZnSO₄·7H₂O, 0.03 g/L MnSO₄·7H₂O, and 0.03 g/L MnSO₄·7H₂O has to be used in the medium for fermentation.

Each experiment is performed in triplicate for 10 days at 30 C and 150 rpm. Samples were taken on a scale to determine total sugar intake and MPs development. Fermentation kinetics investigations were performed out in a 1000 mL Erlenmeyer flask containing 400 mL fermentation media for 14 days. Experiments on the effects of 50-HMF and Fur on MPs production were conducted out like in a 1000 mL Erlenmeyer flask containing 400 mL of glucose-based fermentation medium (GBFM) containing 0.60 g/L of 50-HMF or 0.36 g/L of Fur and 80 g/L of glucose, to the same other compounds as the raw rice straw hydrolysate-based fermentation medium. Because MEB broth contains more free amino acids than PDB broth, MEB broths produced greater red pigment (0.176 OD/mL) than PDB broth (0.123 OD/mL). When compared to submerged fermentation, solid-state fermentation increased pigment production in *Monascus purpureus* MTCC 410. The amount of pigment produced on cooked autoclaved rice (4.4 OD/g) and autoclaved rice (3.11 OD/g) was higher than MEB broth (0.176 OD/mL), and solid-state fermentation produced more biomass than submerged fermentation.

Solid-state fermented autoclaved rice yielded 1.09 g wet biomass, while solid-state fermented autoclaved rice yielded 0.44 g wet biomass (Kaur et al.). *M. sanguineus* mycelial growth and red pigment optimization in potato dextrose broth fungal medium were explored under adverse conditions. About 50 mL of medium had been prepared in 100 mL conical flasks.

After that, it was autoclaved at 121 C for 20 min to disinfect it. After cooling, the sample was inoculated with 0.5 mL of *M. sanguineus* culture and stored at a temperature of 5.5 to protect it. For a total of 16 days, the experiment was kept in a static state. The samples were kept at 30 C for incubation. Glycerol, peptone, and

NaCl stress were studied prior to autoclaving by adding glycerol at concentrations of 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1, and 1.25 M to the media, as well as peptone and NaCl at concentrations of 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1, and 1.25% (w/v) to the media. At 30 C, 40 C, 50 C, 60 C, and 70 C, the spore suspension was tested. The effects of temperature stress were assessed 1 min before inoculation. These spores are obtained from fungi. It was also necessary to apply inoculum (Dikshit & Tallapragada,). Production and Entrepreneurship Plan for Red Pigment from *Monascus* sp. Recovery of *Monascus* Pigment Overnight at 55 C, the fermented materials were dried. The ratios of substrate to solvent differed from one experiment to the next. By using Soxhlet extraction, the pigments were retrieved for 12 h in 95% ethanol under partial vacuum at 65 C. Except where mentioned, static extractions were performed with 1 g of fermented substrate in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks with various organic solvents for 24 h at room temperature. Agitated extractions in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks with 95% ethanol or ethanol-water compositions were done at room temperature for 1 h at 110 rpm on a rotary shaker. The extracts were centrifuged for 15 min at 10,000 g in all cases. Various ethanol: water ratios of 10:0 were used to extract a properly weighed MFDS from roughly 1 g. About 9:1; 8:2; 7:3; 6:4; and 5:5 were filtered through Whatman no. 1 Paper at 30 C or 60 C at 100 rpm for 2 h. The pigment was analyzed using spectrophotometry (Srianta et al.,). Monacolins were extracted from solid and liquid samples of fermented food using somewhat different extraction procedures. The solid fermented product was dried and powdered coarsely. The sample (0.5 g) was incubated for 2 h at 60 C with agitation in 5 mL of ethanol/water solution (75:25), then centrifuged for 10 min at 3000 g. To break the mycelia cells in the liquid fermented product, it was homogenized. The homogenized sample (5 mL) was extracted for 2 h at 60 C with agitation in 5 mL of 95% ethanol before being centrifuged for 10 min at 3000 g. The supernatant (1 mL) from both experiments was concentrated and dried under vacuum before being resolved in 1 mL ACN. Through a membrane filter, the mixture was filtered (Ajdari et al.). Fermented red “mould” rice (10 g) was placed in a 100 mL flask, dissolved in 20 mL acetone, and shaken for 15 min at 25 C in an orbital shaker. The top acetone filtrate was filtered using Whatman filter paper and centrifuged for 10 min at 2500 rpm. Cell-free fermented broth was used to purify the pigments. Scraped off the target band (Rf 0.42), diluted in ethanol, then filtered to remove silica purification of the red pigment generated using preparative TLC was done using semi-preparative HPLC. M. Karthikeyan and D. Dharumadurai Purification of *Monascus* Pigment After extractive fermentation, *Monascus* pigments were produced from fermentation broth. They went from a nonionic surfactant micelle solution to an ionic liquid phase. According to the findings, *Monascus* pigments did not interact with primary amines in an aminophilic manner (Zhong et al.,).

Entrepreneurship Concept in Monascus Pigment Production

Entrepreneurship is described as the ability and willingness to create, organize, and run a business in order to profit, with all of the risks that go along with it. The most visible manifestation of entrepreneurship is the establishment of new companies. An entrepreneur is a person who has the capacity and motivation to establish, manage, and succeed in a new business, as well as the risk that comes with it, in order to profit. Starting a new business venture is the best example of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs are typically referred to as innovators or providers of new ideas since they bring new ideas to market by replacing old ones with new technologies. The goal of productization is to create a product investment that can be mass customized. Companies in the high-tech sector must strike a balance between standardization and customization. Product data management techniques can cut down on engineering time and help a product get to market faster. Marketing and sales are two distinct yet intertwined functions. Marketing and sales may be handled by employees from a variety of divisions inside a major organization. Because they lack the financial resources to hire specialized staff for each, startups usually fail to discern between the two. Both recurring and non-recurring expenses have an impact on a company's cash flow and profitability of Monascus pigment production. Because recurring expenses have a year-over-year influence on profitability, they must be examined, monitored, and controlled to stay within budgeted limits.

Non-recurring expenses are rarely anticipated for, but they can have a significant influence on cash flow and profitability in the year they occur. Non-recurring expenses, such as the price of a new location or new equipment are beneficial since they improve business operations. Non-recurring expenses such as substantial consumable like culture media, chemicals, solvents, laboratory glassware or plasticware, legal fees, costs of ceasing operations, and costs associated with labour unrest, among others, can result in business losses, and their causes should be identified and remedied.

Rice bran is the cheapest source of Monascus production, and it is best suited for the growth as it has optimal nutritional requirement for the growth and development of the strain. It is highly suggested to use rice bran in the production of Monascus pigment. Rice bran has the optimum amount of carbohydrates, proteins, and other trace minerals like phosphorous that is required for the Monascus production.

Conclusions

Monascus pigments have generated global interest due to their potential antimutagenic, anti-tumor, anti-obesity, anti-inflammation, anti-diabetes, and cholesterol-lowering properties. Monascus pigments can be produced with the starter culture of Monascus strain that could be commercially bought and can be made to synthesis the red Monascus pigment through fermentation, namely, solid

state fermentation and submerged fermentation with the easily accessible raw materials of less cost. After fermentation, they could be dried and powdered and easily packaged and then brought out to sale and sold to various firms that requires *Monascus* pigment.

The new entrepreneurs can make out huge profit with commercializing this biopigment as it has got a various attention in various industries. Recurring costs that have to be used are comparatively very less than commercializing other pigments as *Monascus* red pigment grows very well on the substrates like rice bran, jackfruit seeds, corn etc. Out of the aforementioned substrates, rice bran is the main substrate with optimal growth conditions for the *Monascus* strain. Production of *Monascus* pigment and its entrepreneurship plan ideas are illustrated in small-scale production, which could bring out many more entrepreneurs with production of *Monascus* red pigment.

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